

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTION WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART XIII INFLUENCE OF THE STATE OF POLARISATION OF LIGHT ON THE VELOCITY OF PHOTO-OXIDATION OF ORGANIC SUBSTANCES BY HYDROGEN PEROXIDE WITH COLLOIDS AS PHOTSENSITISERS.

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In this part results on the influence of polarised light in bringing about photo-oxidations of organic substances by hydrogen peroxide with inorganic colloids as photosensitisers have been given. Colloids used are (i) tungstic acid sol, (ii) molybdic acid sol, (iii) vanadic acid sol, (iv) chromic tungstate sol, and (v) chromic hydroxide sol.

The kinetics of these reactions in unpolarised light have been studied in detail (*cf.* Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 59). The experimental procedure and arrangement have been described in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 495).

In the present case the reacting systems, immediately after mixing the reagents, were exposed to radiation ($366\mu\mu$) in either *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised state. The velocity of reaction was measured after the induction period was over. The induction period of these photo-oxidations in the circularly polarised light varied from 6 to 8 hours.

Photochemical Oxidation of Organic Substances by Hydrogen Peroxide with Tungstic Acid Sol as Photosensitiser (with or without promoters).

When the concentration of hydrogen peroxide was $0.02M$, which is the concentration of hydrogen peroxide at which reactions described in the present paper are given, the reaction was found to obey unimolecular law.

The concentration of tungstic acid sol (in terms of tungstate equivalent) was 0.025M. The velocity of reaction varied as the square root of absorbed radiation.

TABLE I.

Composition of reaction mixture:—sodium tungstate=0.025M; H_2O_2 =0.02M; glucose=0.025M; HCl=0.08N. Temp. = 30°. λ = 366 μ m. I_{abs} = Intensity of light absorbed in ergs per cm²/sec.

		Unpolarised.	l-Circularly polarised.	d-Circularly polarised.
I_{abs}	...	383	728	728
$K_{unimol} \times 10^4$	...	3.91	5.68	4.21

TABLE II A.

Formaldehyde as reductant.

λ = 366 μ m. Temp = 30°. Tungstate = 0.025M. H_2O_2 = 0.02M. H'CHO = 0.036M. HCl = 0.0877N.

Nature of light used.	I_{abs} .	$K_{unimol} \times 10^4$.
Unpolarised	1931	2.88
l-Circularly polarised	158	0.79
d- ,, polarised	158	0.61

TABLE II B.

Laevulose as reductant.

Laevulose = 0.025M. HCl = 0.078N. Other factors same as in Table II A.

Nature of light used.	I_{abs} .	$K_{unimol} \times 10^4$.
Unpolarised	1931	6.97
l-Circularly polarised	241	2.23
d-Circularly polarised	241	1.98

TABLE III.

Glucose as reductant (in presence of promoters).

$\lambda = 366\mu\mu$. Temp. = 31° . Glucose = $0.025M$. Tungstate = $0.025M$.

Nature of light. I_{abs} . $K_{unimol} \times 10^4$.			Nature of light. I_{abs} . $K_{unimol} \times 10^4$.		
(a) Promoter ($M/2500$) - $FeCl_3, 6H_2O$. $H_2O_2 = 0.01M$. $HCl = 0.08N$.			(b) Promoter ($M/2500$) - $FeCl_3, 6H_2O$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0086M$. $HCl = 0.08N$.		
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	360	4.88	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	360	4.78
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	360	3.91	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	360	3.68
(c) Promoter ($M/20,000$) - $FeSO_4, 7H_2O$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0126M$. $HCl = 0.1175N$.			(d) Promoter ($M/20,000$) - $FeSO_4, 7H_2O$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0159M$. $HCl = 0.1175N$.		
Unpolarised	2980	15.00	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	600	7.82
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	600	7.06	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	600	6.44
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	600	5.52			
(e) Promoter = $M/20,000$ - $CuSO_4, 7H_2O$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0138M$. $HCl = 0.1175N$.					
Unpolarised			2980		15.76
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised			600		7.13
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised			600		5.75

From the above tables it is evident $V_0 = V_l > V_d$, the terms having the usual significance.

Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Hydrogen Peroxide with Chromic Tungstate Sol as Photosensitiser.

This piece of work was taken to investigate the influence of light of different wave-lengths upon this photo-reaction.

Unpublished data by the author on this reaction at $579\mu\mu$ showed that in this case the reaction was always zero-molecular. At $579\mu\mu$ the velocity constant varied directly as the intensity of absorbed radiation but at $366\mu\mu$ it varied as the square root of absorbed radiation. The circularly polarised light in two opposite directions was obtained in two ways (i) with the help of $\lambda/4$ plate or (ii) with the help of Fresnel Rhomb.

TABLE IVA.

Light circularly polarised by $\lambda/4$ plate (as described in Part I).

$\lambda = 579\mu\mu$. Temp. = 29.1° . Glucose = $0.025M$. HCl = $0.039N$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0114$. Chromic tungstate = $0.0265M$.

	Unpolarised.	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised.	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised.
I_{abs}	... 2500	1100	1100
$K_0 \times 10^{10}$	... 7.24	3.32	2.56

TABLE IVB.

$\lambda = 366\mu\mu$. Temp. = 30.5° . $H_2O_2 = 0.0108M$, Chromic tungstate = $0.0082M$. Glucose = $0.025M$. HCl = $0.039N$.

	Unpolarised.	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised.	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised.
I_{abs}	... 505	229	229
$K_{\text{animal}} \times 10^5$	... 2.53	1.69	1.16

Experiments with Fresnel Rhomb.—The experiments at $579\mu\mu$ (cf. Table IV A) were repeated with 1000 c.p. point-o-lite lamp and the Fresnel Rhomb.

Description of the Apparatus.—The polariser consisted of a large Nicol which was fitted with a graduated circle and the vernier attached to the larger circle. The Fresnel Rhomb was set up with its face vertical. When the short axis of Nicol was kept vertical, plane polarised light was obtained. For *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light, the polariser was rotated through 45° from the zero position towards the right and left respectively.

TABLE V.

Region = $579\mu\mu$. Temp. = 30.5° . Glucose = $0.025M$. Tungstate = $0.0265M$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0096M$. HCl = $0.04N$.

Nature of light used.	I_{abs} .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised.	930	2.89
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised.	930	2.77

Thus as before $V_L > V_D$, the terms having the same meaning as before.

Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Hydrogen Peroxide in Acid Medium with Vanadic Acid Sol as Photosensitiser.

The reaction followed the zero-molecular law with respect to hydrogen peroxide and the velocity constant varied as the square root of the intensity of absorbed radiation.

TABLE VI.

$\lambda = 366\mu\mu$. Temp. = 27° . $p_n = 5.0$. Sodium vanadate = $0.033M$. $H_2O_2 = 0.01M$. Acetic acid = $0.018M$. Glucose = $0.05M$.

		Unpolarised.	l-Circularly polarised.	d-Circularly polarised.
I_{abs}	...	1256	307	307
$K_0 \times 10^{10}$	...	5.17	2.56	1.96

From the above table, it is evident that $V_0 = V_L > V_D$, the terms having the usual significance.

Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Hydrogen Peroxide at $p_n 5.2$ with Chromic Hydroxide Sol as Photosensitiser.

The reaction was unimolecular with respect to hydrogen peroxide.

TABLE VII.

Region = $579\mu\mu$. Temp. = 28° . Glucose = $0.025M$. $H_2O_2 = 0.0157M$. Chromic hydroxide = $0.02105M$.

Nature of light used.	I_{abs} .	K_{unimol} with respect to H_2O_2 .
l-Circularly polarised	229	3.56×10^{-4} .
d-Circularly polarised	229	3.56×10^{-4}

From the above table it is evident that $V_L = V_o$, the terms having the usual significance.

Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Hydrogen Peroxide in presence of Molybdic Acid Sol as Photosensitiser.

After the induction period was over, the reaction was always zero-molecular. The velocity constant was directly proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation.

TABLE VIII.

$\lambda = 366\mu$. Temp. = 31° . Alcohol = $4.346M$. HCl = $0.0746N$. Molybdate = $0.05M$. $H_2O_2 = 0.022M$

		Unpolarised.	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised.	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised.
I_{abs}	...	1635	252	252
$K \times 10^{10}$	...	10.79	1.76	1.76

From the above table it is evident that $V_o = V_L = V_o$, the terms having the same significance as before.

From Tables I-VI it is quite evident that under otherwise identical conditions *l*-circularly polarised light is more efficient than *d*-circularly polarised light in bringing about photochemical oxidation with tungstic acid, chromic tungstate and vanadic acid sols as photosensitisers, while in presence of molybdic acid sol and chromic hydroxide sol, light in the two states of circular polarisation is equally efficient.

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